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Research Article

**RESULTS OF LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY IN THE
ELDERLY AND YOUNG PATIENTS**¹Dr Syed Muhammad Ali, ²Dr Zeeshan Zameer, ³Dr Aleesha Sarfraz¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan, ²Sheikh Zayed Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan, ³Wah Medical College, Wah Cantt.**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** to understand the results of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in older patients compared to young patients.**Material and methods:** The study was conducted in the general surgery department of Nishtar Hospital, Multan for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. We divided the patients into 2 groups according to their age, ie under and over 60 years of age. The age, gender, type of surgery and conversion rate of both groups were analyzed and recorded.**Results:** A total of 200 patients underwent cholecystectomy for chronic cholelithiasis in the general surgery department were selected. These 200 patients were divided into 2 groups according to their age. Group 1 included 140 patients aged 60 years. In each group, the majority of patients were female. All patients passed over their knees. cholecystectomy.**Conclusion:** The conclusion is that although laparoscopic cholecystectomy is performed more frequently in younger patients, age is not an important factor for both conversion and incidence; therefore, laparoscopic surgery can be safely performed in elderly patients.**Key words:** shank, the elderly, gallstone disease**Corresponding author:****Dr. Syed Muhammad Ali,**

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INTRODUCTION:

The gold standard in the treatment of gallstones, currently lasting several days, is laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is better than open cholecystectomy and is very well documented, but the procedure is associated with a high frequency of biliary damage. Currently, the first choice of treatment for gallbladder removal in elderly patients is laparoscopic cholecystectomy, especially before the development of complications such as acute cholecystitis or the formation of dense adhesions from chronic cholecystitis, but the safety of this procedure in older patients is still questioned in some studies. This study was conducted to compare the results of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in young patients (<60 years) with elderly patients (> 60 years)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was a randomized, controlled study that assessed the results of laparoscopic cholecystectomy performed in elderly patients v / s. The study was conducted in the general surgery department of Nishtar Hospital, Multan for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. A total of 200 patients of both sexes aged 15 to 70 years with cholelithiasis

visible on ultrasound in the surgical outpatient department were included. Patients with acute cholecystitis, multiple gallbladder cancer abdominal surgery, multiple comorbidities, obstructive jaundice, dilatation of the common bile duct, acute pancreatitis, stones / mass of the common bile duct or requiring intraoperative fluorocholangiography / common bile duct examination were excluded from the study. Patients requiring conversion from laparoscopic to open cholecystectomy for any of the above reasons were also excluded. Patients under the age of 15 or over 70 will be excluded from the study. These 200 patients were divided into 2 groups according to their age. Group 1 consisted of 140 patients aged <60 years, while group 2 consisted of 60 patients aged > 60 years. SPSS version 17 was used for data analysis.

RESULTS:

A total of 200 patients underwent cholecystectomy for chronic gallstone disease were selected. These 200 patients were divided into 2 age groups. Group 1 consisted of 140 patients aged <60 years, while group 2 consisted of 60 patients aged > 60 years. In each group, the majority of patients were women who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy (Table 1).

Table 1: Indications for laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Indications	=n	%age
Chronic cholecystitis	117	58.5
Repeated attacks of biliary colic	50	25
Cholelithiasis (patient's wish)	23	11.5
Acute cholecystitis	10	5

Table 2: Postoperative complications

Complications	Group <60 yrs of age (n=140)	Group >60 yrs of age (n=60)
Port site infection	10(7.1 %)	2(3.3%)
Minor bile leak	5(3.6%)	1(1.6%)
Intraperitoneal collection	6(4.3%)	2(3.3%)
Pulmonary problems (basal atelectasis, pneumonia, pleural effusion etc.)	5(3.6%)	8(13.3%)

After cholecystectomy, the patients stayed in the hospital for one day. Some patients required longer hospital stays due to postoperative complications. All these complications were treated conservatively, in some cases antibiotics (intravenously) were administered, but these patients did not require surgery. All these postoperative complications are presented in the table below, together with the

percentage of patients in both groups, who experienced these complications. Many of the 200 patients who came to us with gallstone disease also had other conditions. All of these comorbidities and the total number of patients with them are discussed in Table 3 below. Of these 200 patients, 17 went from laparoscopic cholecystectomy to open-label cholecystectomy (Table 4).

Table 3: Co morbid conditions

Co morbid	Group <60 yrs of age(n=140)	Group >60 yrs of age (n=60)
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Hypertension	13(9.3%)	10(16.7%)
Diabetes mellitus	7 (5%)	8(5.7%)
COPD	0	5(3.57%)
Hepatitis C	15(10.7%)	5(3.57%)
Hepatitis B	5(3.6%)	2(1.43%)

Table 4: Factors responsible for conversion of laparoscopic cholecystectomy to open cholecystectomy

Factors	Group <60 yrs of age (n=140)	Group >60 yrs of age (n=60)
Difficult anatomy	6(4.3%)	2(3.3%)
Bleeding (intraoperative)	2(1.4%)	2(3.3%)
Adhesions due to previous surgery	4(2.8%)	1(1.7%)
Total	12(8.5%)	5(8.3%)

DISCUSSION:

After the introduction of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, there has been a dramatic change in the treatment of gallstone disease. Complications of gallstone disease are also more common in older patients. Shorter hospital stays, early return to daily activities, and fewer physiological dysfunctions were factors that made laparoscopic cholecystectomy an acceptable and popular method of gallbladder removal. The above-mentioned benefits of laparoscopic cholecystectomy make this procedure an acceptable option for the elderly, suffering from many other comorbidities that sometimes make surgery difficult and dangerous for them. The associated comorbidities of the patients included in our study are quite similar to some other international studies. Some international studies have found that the incidence of acute cholecystitis is higher in elderly patients, but according to our study results, only 10 patients had acute cholecystitis and only 3 of them were > 60 years old. The factors responsible for the conversion from laparoscopic to open cholecystectomy are discussed in Table 3. It is clear that the conversion rate in elderly patients (> 60 years) was 8.3%. This finding is quite similar to other international studies that range from 5% to 25%. According to this study, the conversion rate for young patients was 8.5%. According to the available international literature, increased age of patients is also an important risk factor for the conversion of laparoscopic cholecystectomy to the open method. This can be attributed to a longer history of gallstone disease in the elderly and an increased number of attacks of acute cholecystitis. Reduced morbidity and mortality are the reasons why the laparoscopic approach is preferred in older patients over the open approach to gallbladder removal. This is evidenced by reports that in some international studies the incidence of open cholecystectomy in the elderly is 23–28%, and the mortality rate is 1.5–2%. In laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the elderly, the

reported incidence is 5–15%, and mortality 0–1%. There was no mortality in our study. Cholecystectomies are very difficult to perform in men, but our study did not confirm this fact. Laparoscopic surgery is now considered a more feasible and reliable technique for elderly patients.

CONCLUSION:

Although laparoscopic cholecystectomy is performed more frequently in younger patients, age is not an important factor for both conversion and morbidity; therefore, laparoscopic surgery can be safely performed in elderly patients.

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